

Effectivity of the Consortium of Rhizobacteria and Endophytic Bacteria to Controls the White Tip Disease of Rice Caused by Seed-Borne Nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi*

*Efektivitas Konsorsium Rhizobakteri dan Bakteri Endofit Mengendalikan Penyakit Pucuk Putih Padi Akibat Nematoda Tular Benih *Aphelenchoides besseyi**

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ABSTRAK

Aphelenchoides besseyi merupakan nematoda tular benih yang menyebabkan penyakit pucuk putih pada padi. Kehilangan hasil akibat infeksi nematoda ini berkisar antara 30-50% di berbagai negara. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengetahui efektivitas konsorsium rhizobakteri dan bakteri endofit dalam mengendalikan penyakit pucuk putih sekaligus mendorong pertumbuhan benih padi yang terinfeksi *A. besseyi*. Dilakukan uji kompatibilitas bakteri, uji *in vitro* untuk menguji aktivitas nematisida konsorsium bakteri, dan uji *in vivo* untuk mengetahui efektivitas konsorsium bakteri dalam menekan kejadian penyakit dan mendorong pertumbuhan padi. Penelitian dilaksanakan di Laboratorium Perlindungan Tanaman, Fakultas Pertanian, Universitas Jember sejak Bulan Juli 2020 sampai dengan Bulan Desember 2020. Penelitian ditata menggunakan rancangan acak kelompok dengan lima konsentrasi suspensi bakteri, yaitu 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, dan 100%. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan konsorsium bakteri endofit efektif mengendalikan pertumbuhan *A. besseyi* hingga 80% dibandingkan dengan kontrol. Tingkat penularan penyakit pucuk putih pada tanaman kontrol mencapai 83%. Sebagai perbandingan, gejala penyakit lebih rendah 74,5% hingga 25% pada tanaman yang diberi perlakuan dengan suspensi konsorsium bakteri. Panjang gejala tanaman kontrol mencapai 3,94 cm, sedangkan rata-rata panjang gejala pada tanaman perlakuan berkisar antara 3,41-1,50 cm. Aplikasi bakteri endofit juga mempercepat pertumbuhan tanaman dan panjang akar padi. Efektivitas konsorsium rhizobakteri dan bakteri endofit untuk mengendalikan penyakit pucuk putih sekaligus meningkatkan pertumbuhan tanaman padi di Indonesia pertama kali dilaporkan dalam naskah ini.

Keywords: Padi, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, pengendalian

ABSTRACT

Aphelenchoides besseyi is a seed-borne nematode that causes white-tip disease in rice. Yield losses due to this nematode infection reach 30-50% in various countries. This research aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a consortium of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria in controlling the white tip disease while promoting the growth of rice seeds infected by *A. besseyi*. The experiments conducted were a bacterial compatibility test, *in vitro* test to examine the nematocidal activity of bacterial consortium, and an *in vivo* test to investigate the effectiveness of bacterial consortium to suppress disease occurrence and promote the growth of rice. The research was conducted at the Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember from July 2020 to December 2020. The experiments used a randomized block design with five concentration levels of bacterial suspension of 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100%. The results showed that the endophytic bacterial consortium effectively controlled the growth of *A. besseyi* up to 80% compared to control. Furthermore, the percentage of white tip symptoms in the control plant reached 83%. In comparison, it was observed lower in a range from 74.5% to 25% in plants treated with a suspension of endophytic bacterial consortium. The control plant's symptom length reached 3.94 cm, while the average symptom length in the treated plant ranged from 3.41 cm to 1.50 cm. The application of endophytic bacteria was also found to accelerate plant growth by increasing plant height and root length of the rice plant. The effectiveness of a consortium of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria to control white tip disease while increasing plant growth of rice in Indonesia is first reported in this manuscript.

Keywords: Rice, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, control

INTRODUCTION

Rice is one of the staple foods with high economic value since the majority population of Asia consumes it, particularly in developing countries, such as Indonesia (Widyanti *et al.* 2014). The effort to increase rice production encounters many obstacles, one of them is the infection of seed-borne nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi* (Khan *et al.* 2012). Diana (2018) reported that *Aphelenchoides besseyi* is the most important and devastating plant-parasitic nematode of rice. This nematode has been widely distributed over areas in Indonesia. It is difficult to control the distribution of *A. besseyi* since it is transmitted through seed (Devran *et al.* 2017). The nematode *A. besseyi* is reported to attack the rice plant's crown part, resulting in *white tip* symptoms (Hui *et al.* 2014). This nematode can survive up to three years and two months in infested plants (Das and Swain 2013). Despite its ectoparasitic characteristic, adult and fourth-stage juvenile *A. besseyi* can enter rice flowers and hibernate beneath the seed glumes (Khan *et al.* 2012). Hence, the rice plants infected by this nematode are stunted with the symptom of chlorophyll loss in leaf tips. Tulek and Cobanoglu (2010) reported that *A. besseyi* had caused 43% rice crop loss in Turkey. In a separate report, crop loss due to infection by *A. besseyi* reached 50% in Brazil (Da Silva 1992), 30-50% in China (Wang *et al.* 2004), and 768 kg/ha in India (Muthukrishnan *et al.* 1974).

The nematode *A. besseyi* is known to infect many rice varieties in Indonesia. Supramana (2017) mentioned that the manifestation of *A. besseyi* had been observed in the seed of eight rice varieties, namely SL8SHS, hybrid rice (Hipa-14), IPB-3S, IR-64, Pertiwi-1 (Pak Tiwi), Inpari-31, Pandanwangi Bogor (Sintanur), and Ciherang. Several control measures, including *hot water treatment* (HWT), have been applied, yet infection by *A. besseyi* remains a problem often found in the field (Cuc *et al.* 2010). The use of the HWT technique is found to be less popular among farmers since this technique cannot promote the growth of the rice plant. Farmers are more satisfied with a technique that offers several modes of action, such as the ability to suppress white tip disease while promoting seed growth. This problem can be solved by applying biological agents from the group of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria. According to some previous reports, bacteria from the group of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria could play a role as agents that provide seed protection and suppress various seed-borne diseases in many plants (Grobolak *et al.* 2015).

In the previous study, six isolates of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria were discovered from many locations and plant tissues. The isolates were tested for

their physiological activity and reported to have the ability to fix N, dissolve P, play a role as mycorrhiza-helper bacteria, and produce protease enzyme. Moreover, the isolates can also suppress parasitic nematodes' growth in plants, such as *Globodera rosthociensis* in potatoes and *Pratylenchus coffeae* in the coffee plant Asyiah *et al.* (2015; 2018). However, the six isolates' effectiveness in controlling seed-borne nematode *A. besseyi* in rice plants has not yet been investigated.

Several previous reports mentioned that biological agents used to protect seed has great potential in the future (Sharma *et al.* 2015). Besides suppressing the growth of pathogens, biological agents from the bacteria group could also enhance plant growth. The application of biological agents from rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria to increase rice plant growth through seed immersion has been widely reported (Dharam and Maheshwari 2001; Singh and Maheswar 2001). Verma *et al.* (2018) found that endophytic bacteria can increase rice seed length and the percentage of rice seed germination. Agustiansyah *et al.* (2013) claim that rhizobacteria that are isolated from roots could produce HCN, siderophore, and plant growth regulators, induce systemic resistance, and increase uptake of plant nutrition such as phosphate. In addition to rhizobacteria, endophytic bacteria from dry land paddy also produce a potential metabolism as a biocontrol agent and plant growth stimulant (Munif and Wiyono 2012). In another case, Zainudin *et al.* (2014) said that rhizobacteria can reduce the attack of downy mildew in corn up to 50% by producing various compounds or metabolites such as siderophore, α -1,3 glucanase, chitinase, antibiotics, and cyanide and can increase plant growth by increasing the concentration of IAA, gibberellin, and cytokinins. Rais *et al.* (2016) claim that *Bacillus* significantly suppressed blast disease and increased the yield of rice plants.

The application of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria as agents to protect seeds has a bright prospect. Both types of bacteria have the ability to directly and indirectly protect the seed (O'callaghan *et al.* 2006). In terms of direct protection, it is reported that rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria produce a wide variety of compounds with antimicrobial activity (Beneduzi *et al.* 2012). Moreover, both types of bacteria indirectly protect the seed by stimulating plants to produce compounds to protect themselves, such as PR-protein, tannin, saponin, and others (Fiori *et al.* 2013). Gupta *et al.* (2015) conclude that rhizobacteria have biofertilizer activity like phosphate solubilization, nitrogen fixation, siderophore production, potassium solubilization, phytohormone production and biopesticide activity like antibiotics production, induced systemic resistance (ISR), hydrolytic enzymes production, siderophore production, and

exopolysaccharides production.

The use of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria to promote rice growth is more effective if applied in a consortium compared to a single isolate (Munif *et al.* 2019). The consortium application allows the production of a higher amount and diversity of secondary metabolites that can increase plant growth (Asyiah *et al.* 2020). This research aimed to examine the effectiveness of a consortium of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria to control seed-borne nematode *A. besseyi* in rice plants and suppress *white tip* disease in rice and increase the growth of rice seed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted at the Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java, Indonesia from July 2020 to December 2020.

Isolates of Rhizobacteria and Endophytic Bacteria

Bacterial isolates used in this study were previously isolated and identified. The detail of the isolates used in this research is presented in Table 1.

Compatibility Test of Bacterial Isolates

The compatibility test was aimed to investigate the compatibility between isolates used in this study. The test was performed using the technique of paper disk diffusion. Each isolate was grown in Tryptic Soy Broth liquid media (TSB, HiMedia, India) for 48 hours at a temperature of 32°C in a petri dish with a diameter of 9 cm. About 100 µl of solvent was obtained from each isolate to be poured evenly on Tryptic Soy Agar media (TSA, HiMedia, India). Later, sterile filter paper at a diameter of 0.5 cm was placed onto the surface of agar media. A drop of 25 µl of other bacterial suspension was

put on the filter paper and incubated for 48 hours. Sterile aquadest was used as the negative control, while ethanol at 70% concentration was used as the positive control. Compatibility was indicated by the absence of a clear zone around the filter paper (Asyiah *et al.* 2020).

Production of Bacterial Consortium

Approximately 1 ml of bacterial suspension that has been grown for 48 hours from each bacterial isolate was taken and mixed with 192 ml of TSB media. The volume of mixed TSB media and the suspension of eight bacterial isolates was 200 ml; this suspension was further called consortium. Later, the consortium was incubated at a temperature of 32°C for 48 hours while shaking at 250 rpm. The density of consortium cells produced reached 10⁹. The consortium successfully produced was used for the further test (Asyiah *et al.* 2020).

Rice Seed and Source of Nematode Inoculum

The rice seed used in this study was the seed of Pak Tiwi-1 variety commercially sold in Indonesia. The Pak Tiwi-1 variety selection referred to the result of a study conducted by Ibrahim (2019) which reported that the variety is mostly infected and vulnerable to infection by *A. besseyi*. To confirm whether the seeds used in this study contained *A. besseyi* inoculum, extraction and calculation of the average population of nematode per 5 g seed were done prior to further testing. Extraction was performed following the standard of ISTA (2014).

In Vitro Test to Investigate the Effectiveness of Bacterial Consortium as Bionematicide

A total of 50 nematodes *Aphelenchoides besseyi* in 9 ml sterile aquadest were placed into a petri dish at a 3 cm diameter. Moreover, about 1 ml of bacterial consortium suspension at different concentrations was put into the petri dish containing nematode to be further incubated for six hours. Nematodes were rinsed afterward and transferred to sterile aquadest, and incubated for 10 minutes to be further observed for their mortality rate. The nematodes' mortality was indicated by the absence of movement response from nematodes during mortality observation and when they were touched using an observation needle (Mendoza *et al.* 2008).

The concentrations used in this study were 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100%. Control treatments applied were sterile aquadest (K-) and TSB media (K+) without bacteria. This test was conducted in the laboratory under a uniform environmental condition; thus, the experimental design applied was the completely randomized design with four replications. Mortality data

Table 1. Isolates of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria used in this research. Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java (December 2015)

Isolate code	Bacterial species	Status	Reference
PD01	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Rhizobacteria	
BS01	<i>Pseudomonas dimunita</i>	Rhizobacteria	
SK07	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Endophyte	
SK14	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Endophyte	Asyiah et al. (2015; 2018)
SK15	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Endophyte	
KB11	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Endophyte	
KB14	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Endophyte	
KB63	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Endophyte	

of nematode *A. besseyi* (%) were further transformed according to the Arcsin transformation formula and analyzed using analysis of variance, followed by Duncans' Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the confidence level of 95%. The program used for analysis was DSAASTAT version 1.101.

In Vitro Test to Investigate the Effectiveness of Bacterial Consortium to Suppress White Tip Disease and Accelerate the Growth of Rice Seed

A total of 50 rice seeds for each treatment and replication were immersed in 50 ml of bacterial consortium suspension at various concentrations for sixty minutes. The concentration of bacterial consortium applied in this study included 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100%. The control treatment used was sterile aquadest (K-) and TSB media (K+) without bacteria. The research was conducted in a greenhouse by following the experimental randomized block design with seven treatments, four replications, and each replication used 50 rice seeds. The treated rice seeds were further grown for 14 days in sterile soil. The pathology parameters observed were the occurrence of white tip symptom and white tip symptom length in each treatment. Moreover, the growth parameters investigated included seed height and root length. Data were analyzed using analysis of variance, followed by Duncans' Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at a confidence level of 95%. The program used for analysis was DSAASTAT version 1.101 (Xie *et al.* 2019).

RESULTS

Compatibility of Bacterial Isolates

Based on the result of the compatibility test, all isolates were found to be compatible to combine. Compatibility is indicated by the absence of a clear zone or halo surrounding the paper disk area where bacteria were

Table 2. Compatibility of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria. Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java, July-December 2020

Isolate	PD01	BS01	SK07	SK14	SK15	KB11	KB14	KB63
PD01								
BS01	"							
SK07	"	"						
SK14	"	"	"					
SK15	"	"	"	"				
KB11	"	"	"	"	"			
KB14	"	"	"	"	"	"		
KB63	"	"	"	"	"	"	"	

Note: (") compatible

dropped onto. The result of this test shows that all isolates used in this study are safe to be cultured together (Table 2).

Extraction of Nematode from Rice Seed

Based on the result of extraction, it is known that 223-258 nematodes with an average number of 247.32 ± 8.71 were obtained in every 5 g of seeds. Nematodes extracted were confirmed as *A. besseyi* in accordance with the morphological and morphometric characteristics.

Effectiveness of Bacterial Consortium as Bionematicide (In Vitro)

According to the observation result, no nematodes were found dead in control treatments. All nematodes observed in this study showed a movement response during observation and when they were touched using the observation needle. This result indicated that nematode mortality in other treatments was not affected by aquadest and TSB media. Furthermore, in treatment with 20% consortium suspension, the average mortality of nematodes was 2.5%. Based on the statistical analysis, nematode mortality in treatment with 20% bacterial consortium suspension was not significantly different from the control treatment. In treatment with 40% bacterial consortium suspension, the total mortality of *A. besseyi* reached 14%, as indicated by the absence of movement response during observation and when it was touched using the observation needle. The mortality rate of nematode in this study was significantly different compared to the control treatment, with both controls using sterile aquadest and TSB media.

Further, in treatment with 60% bacterial consortium suspension, the average mortality of nematode observed was 30.50%, indicating a significant difference in result compared to the previously discussed results. The mortality rate of nematode is increasing along with the increase in the concentration of bacterial consortium suspension. In treatment with 80% bacterial

Table 3. Mortality of *A. besseyi* at different concentration of bacterial consortium. Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java, July-December 2020

Treatment	Mortality $\pm$ SD (%)
Aquadest	0.00 ^a $\pm$ 0.00
TSB media	0.00 ^{ab} $\pm$ 0.00
20% consortium	2.50 ^{ac} $\pm$ 3.00
40% consortium	14.00 ^d $\pm$ 8.49
60% consortium	30.50 ^e $\pm$ 3.42
80% consortium	40.50 ^e $\pm$ 3.42
100% consortium	80.50 ^f $\pm$ 6.40

Figure 1. Correlation between bacterial consortium concentration and *A. besseyi* mortality. Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java, July-December 2020.

consortium suspension, the average mortality rate of nematode was approximately 40.50%, reflecting a significant difference from control treatment, yet it was not statistically different from treatment with 60% bacterial consortium suspension. In the highest concentration of 100% bacterial consortium suspension, the average nematode mortality rate reached 80.50%. This value was the highest mortality rate obtained, which was also significantly different from all treatments tested. Moreover, data on the mortality rate of *A. besseyi* are presented in Table 3.

In this test, the high concentration of bacterial consortium was correlated with the mortality rate of *A. besseyi*. A value of 0.93 was obtained from this correlation test, showing a positive and very strong correlation between the concentration of bacterial consortium and nematode mortality. Moreover, the graph of correlation is depicted in Figure 1.

Effectiveness of Bacterial Consortium to Control White Tip Disease in Rice

Based on the observation result, out of 50 rice seeds planted, an average of 83.00% of the control plant treated with sterile aquadest showed white tip symptoms. Simultaneously, a lower value of 80.50% was observed in the control plant treated with TSB media. Statistically, there is no significant difference between the plant treated with aquadest and TSB media. Therefore, any difference between treatments with the bacterial consortium is affected by bacterial cells.

In treatment with 20% bacterial consortium suspension, the average number of plants showing the symptom reached 74.50%. Despite the lower percentage compared to that using TSB media, no statistically different result was observed. This indicates that bacterial consortium is not yet effective in suppressing white tip

disease due to infection by *A. besseyi*. Furthermore, in treatment with 40% consortium suspension, the average number of plants observed with this symptom was 42%, significantly different from the control plant. In treatment with 60% bacterial consortium suspension, an average 39% of seed grown with this symptom. Even though the result was significantly different from the control, treatment with 60% bacterial consortium suspension was not significantly different from treatment with 40% bacterial consortium suspension.

The occurrence of white tip disease continued to be lower along with the higher concentration of bacterial consortium. In treatment with 80% bacterial consortium suspension, an average of 34% of seeds were observed to have white tip symptoms. This value was significantly different from the plant in the control treatment, but not significantly different from treatment with 60% bacterial consortium suspension. The highest 100% bacterial consortium suspension concentration showed a lower average white tip symptom of 25%. Moreover, data of white tip symptom percentage are illustrated in Figure 2A.

Results of observation about symptom length in

Figure 2. Effect of different bacterial consortium concentration on the percentage and length of white tip symptom. Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java, July-December 2020.

Figure 3. Correlation between bacterial consortium concentration and the percentage of white tip symptom (A) and length of white tip symptom (B). Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java. July-December 2020.

each treatment also showed a similar pattern to the percentage of white tip symptoms in rice seed. In the control plant treated with aquadest and TSB media, the average white tip symptom length was 3.91 cm and 3.94 cm, respectively. In control treatment with aquadest and TSB media, no significant or statistically different result was observed. Furthermore, in treatment with 20% bacterial consortium suspension, symptom length reached 3.54 cm, followed by treatment with 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100% bacterial suspension, which produced average symptom length of 3.41 cm, 3.24 cm, 2.86 cm, and 1.50 cm, respectively. If compared with control treatment, only treatment with 20% bacterial consortium suspension was not significantly different from the control plant. In other treatments, symptom length was significantly different from control, yet the best performance was obtained by treatment with 100% bacterial consortium suspension. Further, data of symptom length in each treatment are depicted in Figure 2B.

Based on the observation result, it is found that the concentration of bacterial consortium is strongly yet negatively correlated with white tip symptom and white tip symptom length due to infection by *A. besseyi*. The value of the correlation between the concentration of bacterial consortium suspension and white tip symptom and white tip symptom length reached -0.94 and -0.88, respectively. Both values reflect a strong correlation between the concentration used and the variables observed. Furthermore, the correlation between the concentration of bacterial consortium and the occurrence of white tip and white tip symptom length is presented in Figure 3.

Effectiveness of Bacterial Consortium in Accelerating the Growth of Rice Seed Infected by *A. besseyi*

Based on the test result, the control plant’s average height

only treated with aquadest was approximately 11.85 cm. This value was not significantly different from the average height of the plant in control of TSB media (11.88 cm), 20% bacterial consortium suspension (11.85), and 40% bacterial consortium suspension (12.33). A significantly different result was observed in the growth of seed treated with 60% bacterial consortium suspension (13.08 cm). In the treatment of 80% bacterial consortium suspension, plant height reached 13.80 cm, while the highest value was observed in plants treated with 100% bacterial consortium suspension, which produced an average plant height of 13.98 cm. However, treatment with 80% bacterial consortium suspension was not significantly different from treatment with 100% bacterial consortium suspension. Based on the data, treatment using 60-100% bacterial consortium suspension could accelerate plant height in a range from 10.37% to 17.97%.

Concerning the variable of root length observation, it is found that root length in aquadest control (2.68 cm) was not significantly different from root length in treatment with TSB media (2.40 cm) and 20% bacterial consortium suspension (2.80 cm). A significant different was investigated in treatment with 40% bacterial consortium suspension (3.48 cm), followed by 60% bacterial consortium suspension (3.98 cm), 80% bacterial consortium suspension (4.15 cm), and 100% bacterial consortium suspension (4.30 cm). According to the data, treatment using 40% bacterial consortium suspension to 100% bacterial consortium could accelerate rice’s root length in a range of 45% - 79.16%. Moreover, data about plant height and root length are listed in Table 4.

According to the observation result, it is known that a higher concentration of bacterial consortium used resulted in higher growth performance of rice seed infected by *A. besseyi* as shown by the correlation value between the concentration of bacterial suspension and plant height, which reached 0.88, and between the concentration of bacterial suspension and root length which amounted to 0.90. Both values indicate a very strong correlation between the concentration of

Table 4. Plant height and root length of rice seed at different concentrations of bacterial consortium. Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java. July-December 2020.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Root length (cm)
Aquadest	11.85 ^a ± 0.55	2.68 ^a ± 0.62
TSB media	11.88 ^a ± 0.33	2.40 ^a ± 0.26
20% consortium	11.85 ^a ± 0.37	2.80 ^a ± 0.22
40% consortium	12.33 ^a ± 0.62	3.48 ^b ± 0.39
60% consortium	13.08 ^b ± 0.56	3.98 ^{bc} ± 0.28
80% consortium	13.80 ^c ± 0.39	4.15 ^c ± 0.17
100% consortium	13.98 ^c ± 0.43	4.30 ^c ± 0.29

Figure 4. Correlation between bacterial consortium concentration and plant height (A) and root length (B). Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java, July-December 2020.

bacterial consortium and growth performance. Besides, the correlation between the concentration of bacterial consortium and growth variables is illustrated in Figure 4.

Correlation Among Observation Variables

Based on the result of observation, it is known that the ability of bacterial consortium to kill *in vitro* the nematode is strongly correlated with the ability of consortium to control symptom (-0.84), suppress white tip symptom length (-0.94), and increase plant height (0.84) also closely correlated with the ability of bacteria in increasing root length (0.79). Furthermore, white tip symptom percentage white tip is also strongly correlated with symptom length (0.79) and very strongly correlated with plant height (-0.80) and root length (-0.88). Symptom length was also closely correlated with plant height (-0.75) and root length (-0.72). Also, plant height was observed to have a robust correlation with root length (0.81). The data of correlation among variables of observation are presented in Table 5.

DISCUSSION

In this study, it was found that bacterial consortium effectively killed *in vitro* the nematode *A. besseyi*. The use of biological control agents from the group of bacteria to control *A. besseyi* has been previously reported by Wang *et al.* (2008). Rhizobacteria and

endophytic bacteria were observed to effectively control different nematodes in many plants. Munif *et al.* (2019) reported that the use of endophytic bacterial consortium originated from forestry plants effectively killing the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne* spp *in vitro*. In another study, Wang *et al.* (2008) reported that suspension from bacterial isolate Snb331 effectively killed nematode *A. besseyi* in a range between 18.09% to 87.24%. The mortality rate of *A. besseyi* continues to increase along with the increasing concentration and duration of immersion. Nematode mortality is expected to have resulted from secondary metabolites produced by bacteria. Afzal *et al.* (2017) reported that members of genera *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Streptomyces* showed positive chitinase and protease as secondary metabolites that act as a nematicide. Furthermore, another metabolite is found to be volatile, such as cyanide (HCN).

Protease is an enzyme with the ability to degrade or transform protein into a more simple structure (Alam *et al.* 2017). Moreover, chitinase is an enzyme that can degrade or transform chitin into a more simple structure (Kim *et al.* 2017). The nematode body structure mostly consists of protein and chitin; thus, degradation by protease and chitinase may result in nematode death. Furthermore, HCN is also reported to be toxic with nematicidal activity for several nematodes. Cronin *et al.* (1997) and Tian *et al.* (2000) reported that chitinase-producing bacteria effectively suppressed the population of nematode *Globodera rostochiensis* besides inhibiting its egg hatching. Another report by Van Nguyen *et al.* (2007) showed that chitinase produced by *Lecanicillium antillanum* B-3 effectively suppressed the population of *Meloidogyne incognita* and its egg hatching. In a separate report by Siddiqui *et al.* (2005), extracellular proteolytic enzyme (protease) from *Pseudomonas fluorescens* CHA0 was one of the major factors causing the isolate to control nematode *M. incognita*. Another report by Qihong *et al.* (2006) mentioned that *Bacillus* sp. B16 could control several types of nematodes through its protease enzyme, which was identified as its pathogenic factor. Jha dan Modi

Table 5. Correlation among observation variables. Plant Protection Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Jember, East Java. July-December 2020.

	Mortality (<i>in vitro</i>)	Percentage of Symptom	Length of Symptom	Plant Height	Root Length
Mortality (<i>in vitro</i>)	1.00				
Percentage of Symptom	-0.84**	1.00			
Length of Symptom	-0.94**	0.79*	1.00		
Plant Height	0.84**	-0.80**	-0.75*	1.00	
Root Length	0.79*	-0.88**	-0.72*	0.81**	1.00

(2018) noted that chitinase from *Streptomyces rubiginosus* SP24 may control root-knot nematode infection in *Vigna radiate*. Munif *et al.* (2020) also reported that chitinase and protease production from biocontrol agents could destroy nematode stylet.

This research also showed that seed treated with bacterial consortium obtained lower symptom percentage and symptom length compared to the seed untreated. This outcome is expected to be closely related to the ability of bacteria in killing nematodes. Also, rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria were reported to induce plant resistance, known as induced systemic resistance, plant resistance over a broad spectrum (Pieterse *et al.* 2014). This induction was stimulated by an elicitor, which involves the coordination and expression of specific genes, also marked by the accumulation of certain compounds such as salicylic acid or jasmonic acid (Harel *et al.* 2013; Mehari *et al.* 2015). This induction works by affecting the physiological characteristics of plants in the absence of new gene introduction. Adam *et al.* (2014) and Hu *et al.* (2018) mentioned that induced systemic resistance could suppress the infection by nematode *M. incognita* in tomatoes. In a separate report, induced systemic resistance was investigated as an effective and efficient technique to control many parasitic nematodes. The low symptom percentage and symptom length of white tip disease in rice plants given treatment are also expected to be correlated with the mortality rate of nematode in seed within the treatment. Togashi and Hoshino (2001) observed that the white tip's symptom percentage was in line with the number of nematodes in the seed.

This study also found that plants given the treatment of bacterial consortium suspension grew better than control plants. It is expected due to the ability of bacteria to produce compounds that might stimulate plant growth. Rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria were observed to fix N, dissolve P, and produce phytohormone like IAA (Vejan *et al.* 2016). In a separate study, Verma *et al.* (2018) reported that applying endophytic bacteria to rice seed could increase rice seed growth by up to 70% compared to the control plant. Moreover, the application of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria with phosphate solvent could also enhance rice seed growth (Lee *et al.* 2019). In another study, IAA-producing rhizobacteria effectively accelerated the growth of rice seeds (Ng *et al.* 2012). These findings are in accordance with and confirm the result of this study.

In the test of correlation among variables, a close correlation between pathology and growth was observed. This finding is in line with the study reported by El-Shafeey *et al.* (2014) that symptoms due to infection by *A. besseyi* will hinder the photosynthesis process, thus

adversely affecting plant growth. Moreover, leaf tissue damage due to infection by *A. besseyi* could also decrease rice production (Tülek *et al.* 2014). Photosynthesis in rice plants is disturbed if parts of leaves are damaged, for example, due to infection by *A. besseyi*. Furthermore, the stress in plants resulting from infection by *A. besseyi* is considered a factor that inhibits rice plant growth (Youssef 2014).

CONCLUSION

The result of this research completes the information about the consortium of rhizobacteria and endophytic bacteria that is effectively applied as the agent to control *A. besseyi* in rice, besides its dual roles as a plant growth promoter. The occurrence of the symptom (symptom percentage) and symptom length in rice seed also can inhibit rice seed growth. In further research, it is necessary to formulate to increase the effectiveness and shelf-life of the endophytic bacterial consortium.

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REFERENCES

- Adam, M., Heuer, H., and Hallmann, J. 2014. Bacterial antagonists of fungal pathogens also control root-knot nematodes by induced systemic resistance of tomato plants. *PLoS One* 9(2), e90402.
- Afzal, I., Iqbal, I., Shinwari, Z.K., and Yasmin, A. 2017. Plant growth-promoting potential of endophytic bacteria isolated from roots of wild *Dodonaea viscosa* L. *Plant Growth Regulation* 81(3), 399–408.
- Alam, M.G., Uddin, M.E., Rahman, S., Ahmad, T., Karim, M.R., Mahmood, M.S., Alam, M.S., Nazmuzzaman, M., Hossain, M.J., and Maitra, P. 2017. Protease activity of extracellular enzyme produced by *B. subtilis* isolated from soil. *Int J Environ Agric Biotechnol.* 2, 382–388.
- Asyiah, I. N., Mudakir, I., Hoesain, M., Pradana, A. P., Djunaidy, A., and Sari, R.F. 2020. Consortium of endophytic bacteria and rhizobacteria effectively suppresses the population of *Pratylenchus coffeae* and promotes the growth of Robusta coffee. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity* 21(10).
- Asyiah, I.N., Soekarto, S., Hoesain, M., Iqbal, M., Hindersah, R., Narulita, E. & Mudakir, I. 2018. The Endophytic Bacteria Isolation as Biological Control Agent of *Pratylenchus Coffeae*. *Asian Journal of Microbiology, Biotechnology and Environmental Sciences* 20 (1): 165-171.
- Asyiah, I.N., Wiryadiputra, S., Fauzi, I., and Harni, R. 2015. *Populasi Pratylenchus coffeae (Z.) dan Pertumbuhan Bibit Kopi Arabika Akibat Inokulasi Pseudomonas diminuta L. dan Bacillus subtilis (C.)*. *Pelita Perkebunan* 31 (1): 30-40.

- Beneduzi, A., Ambrosini, A., and Passaglia, L.M.P. 2012. Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR): their potential as antagonists and biocontrol agents. *Genetics and Molecular Biology*, 35, 1044–1051.
- Cronin, D., Moënné-Loccoz, Y., Dunne, C., and O'gara, F. 1997. Inhibition of egg hatch of the potato cyst nematode *Globodera rostochiensis* by chitinase-producing bacteria. *European Journal of Plant Pathology* 103(5), 433–440.
- Cuc, N. T. T., Son, N. T., Trung, T. M., vân Trang, N., Đang, L. M., and Pilon, M. 2010. Hot water treatment prevents *Aphelenchoides besseyi* damage to *Polianthes tuberosa* crops in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam. *Crop Protection* 29(6), 599–602.
- Da Silva, G. S. 1992. White tip and national rice production. *Informe Agropecuario Belo Horizonte* 16, 57–59.
- Das, N. and Swain, P.K. 2013. Survival and persistence of foliar nematode, *Aphelenchoides besseyi* infecting tuberose. *Indian Journal of Nematology* 43(2), 215–217.
- Devran, Z., Tülek, A., Mýstanođlu, Ý., Çiftçiđil, T. H., and Özalp, T. 2017. A rapid molecular detection method for *Aphelenchoides besseyi* from rice tissues. *Australasian Plant Pathology* 46(1), 43–48.
- Diana, D. R. 2018. Distribusi Nematoda Pucuk Putih Padi *Aphelenchoides besseyi* di Pulau Jawa. *Jurnal Fitopatologi Indonesia* 14(4), 129.
- El-Shafeey, E.I., El-Shafey, R.A.S., Abdel-Hadi, M.A., and Sehly, M.R. 2014. Quantitative and qualitative losses in yield of some rice cultivars due to white tip nematode (*Aphelenchoides besseyi*) infection under Egyptian field conditions. *Jordan Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 10(3).
- Fiori, G.M.L., Fachin, A.L., Correa, V.S.C., Bertoni, B.W., Giuliatti, S., Amui, S.F., de Castro França, S., and Pereira, A.M.S. 2013. Antimicrobial activity and rates of tannins in *Stryphnodendron adstringens* Mart. accessions collected in the Brazilian Cerrado. *American Journal of Plant Sciences* 4(11), 2193.
- Grobelak, A., Napora, A. and Kacprzak, M. 2015. Using plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) to improve plant growth. *Ecological Engineering* 84, 22–28.
- Gupta, G., Parihar, S.S., Ahirwar, N.K., Snehi, S.K., and Singh, V. 2015. Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR): current and future prospects for development of sustainable agriculture. *J Microb Biochem Technol.* 7(2), 96–102.
- Harel, Y. M., Mehari, Z. H., Elad, Y., Rav-David, D., Borenstein, M., Shulchani, R., and Graber, E. R. 2013. Induced systemic resistance in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) by biochar soil amendment. *IOBC/WPRS Bulletin* 86, 59–64.
- Hu, H., Wang, C., Li, X., Tang, Y., Wang, Y., Chen, S., and Yan, S. 2018. RNA Seq identification of candidate defense genes targeted by endophytic *Bacillus cereus* mediated induced systemic resistance against *Meloidogyne incognita* in tomato. *Pest Management Science* 74(12), 2793–2805.
- Hui, F., WEI, L., LIN, M., and ZHOU, Y. 2014. Assessment of rice cultivars in China for field resistance to *Aphelenchoides besseyi*. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture* 13(10), 2221–2228.
- Ibrahim, A. Y. 2019. Keefektifan Kitosan untuk Pengendalian Nematoda Pucuk Putih Padi (*Aphelenchoides besseyi* Christie) melalui Perlakuan Benih. Thesis. Jember: Universitas Jember. (halaman tidak diketahui, website error)
- Jha, S. and Modi, H.A. 2018. Statistical optimization of chitinase production by *Streptomyces rubiginosus* SP24 and efficacy of purified chitinase to control root-knot nematode infection in *Vigna radiata* under controlled conditions. *Chemical and Biological Technologies in Agriculture* 5(1), 1–13.
- Khan, M. R., Handoo, Z. A., Rao, U., Rao, S. B., and Prasad, J. S. 2012. Observations on the foliar nematode, *Aphelenchoides besseyi*, infecting tuberose and rice in India. *Journal of Nematology* 44(4), 391.
- Kim, Y. H., Park, S.K., Hur, J.Y., and Kim, Y.C. 2017. Purification and characterization of a major extracellular chitinase from a biocontrol bacterium, *Paenibacillus elgii* HOA73. *The Plant Pathology Journal* 33(3), 318.
- Lee, K.-E., Adhikari, A., Kang, S.-M., You, Y.-H., Joo, G.-J., Kim, J.-H., Kim, S.-J., and Lee, I.-J. 2019. Isolation and characterization of the high silicate and phosphate solubilizing novel strain *Enterobacter ludwigii* GAK2 that promotes growth in rice plants. *Agronomy* 9(3), 144.
- Mehari, Z. H., Elad, Y., Rav-David, D., Graber, E.R., and Harel, Y.M. 2015. Induced systemic resistance in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) against *Botrytis cinerea* by biochar amendment involves jasmonic acid signaling. *Plant and Soil* 395(1), 31–44.
- Mendoza, A.R., Kiewnick, S., and Sikora, R.A. 2008. In vitro activity of *Bacillus firmus* against the burrowing nematode *Radopholus similis*, the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* and the stem nematode *Ditylenchus dipsaci*. *Biocontrol Science and Technology* 18(4), 377–389.
- Munif, A., Supramana, S., Herliyana, E.N., and Pradana, A.P. 2019. Endophytic Bacterial Consortium Originated from Forestry Plant Roots and Their Nematicidal Activity against *Meloidogyne incognita* Infestation in Greenhouse. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis* 67, 1171–1182.
- Munif, A., and Wiyono, S. 2012. Isolasi bakteri endofit asal padi gogo dan potensinya sebagai agens biokontrol dan pemacu pertumbuhan. *Jurnal Fitopatologi Indonesia* 8(3), 57.
- Munif, A., Wulandari, R.R., and Pradana, A.P. 2020. Biocontrol potential of endophytic bacteria originated from roots of *Ravenala madagascariensis* against *Fusarium oxysporum* and banana-parasitic nematodes. *Pakistan Journal of Phytopathology* 32(1), 79–88.
- Muthukrishnan, T.S., Rajendran, G., and Chandrasekaran, J. 1974. Studies on the white-tip nematode of rice, *Aphelenchoides besseyi* in Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Nematology* 4(2), 188–193.
- Ng, L.C., Sariah, M., Sariam, O., Radziah, O., and Zainal Abidin, M.A. 2012. Rice seed bacterization for promoting germination and seedling growth under aerobic cultivation system. *Australian Journal of Crop Science* 6(1), 170–175.
- O'callaghan, M., Swaminathan, J., Lottmann, J., Wright, D.A., and Jackson, T.A. 2006. Seed coating with biocontrol strain *Pseudomonas fluorescens* F113. *New Zealand Plant Protection* 59, 80–85.
- Pieterse, C.M.J., Zamioudis, C., Berendsen, R.L., Weller, D.M., Van Wees, S.C.M., and Bakker, P.A.H.M. 2014. Induced systemic resistance by beneficial microbes. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 52, 347–375.
- QiuHong, N., Xiaowei, H., Baoyu, T., Jinkui, Y., Jiang, L., Lin, Z., and Keqin, Z. 2006. *Bacillus* sp. B16 kills nematodes with a serine protease identified as a pathogenic factor. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 69(6), 722–730.
- Rais, A., Shakeel, M., Hafeez, F.Y., and Hassan, M.N. 2016. Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria suppress blast disease caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* and increase grain yield of rice. *BioControl* 61(6), 769–780.
- Sharma, K.K., Singh, U.S., Sharma, P., Kumar, A., and Sharma, L. 2015. Seed treatments for sustainable agriculture-A review. *Journal of Applied and Natural Science* 7(1), 521–539.

- Siddiqui, I.A., Haas, D., and Heeb, S. 2005. Extracellular protease of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* CHA0, a biocontrol factor with activity against the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita*. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 71(9), 5646–5649.
- Singh, D. and Maheshwari, V.K. 2001. Biological seed treatment for the control of loose smut of wheat. *Indian Phytopathology* 54(4), 457–460.
- Suprama. 2017. Status *Aphelenchoides besseyi* Christie nematoda terbawa benih padi di Indonesia. Simposium Nasional Fitopatologi: Kemunculan Penyakit Baru, 10 Januari 2017, Bogor, Indonesia.
- Tian, H., Riggs, R.D., and Crippen, D.L. 2000. Control of soybean cyst nematode by chitinolytic bacteria with chitin substrate. *Journal of Nematology* 32(4), 370.
- Togashi, K. and Hoshino, S. 2001. Distribution pattern and mortality of the white tip nematode, *Aphelenchoides besseyi* (Nematoda: Aphelenchoididae), among rice seeds. *Nematology* 3(1), 17–24.
- Tülek, A., Ates, S. S., Akin, K., Surek, H., Kaya, R., and Kepenekci, I. 2014. Determining yield losses in rice cultivars resulting from rice white tip nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi* in field condition. *Pakistan Journal of Nematology* 32(2), 149–154.
- Tulek, A. and Cobanoglu, S. 2010. Distribution of the rice white tip nematode, *Aphelenchoides besseyi*, in rice growing areas in the Thrace region of Turkey. *Nematologia Mediterranea*.
- Van Nguyen, N., Kim, Y.-J., Oh, K.-T., Jung, W.-J., and Park, R.-D. 2007. The role of chitinase from *Lecanicillium antillanum* B-3 in parasitism to root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* eggs. *Biocontrol Science and Technology* 17(10), 1047–1058.
- Vejan, P., Abdullah, R., Khadiran, T., Ismail, S., and Nasrulhaq Boyce, A. 2016. Role of plant growth promoting rhizobacteria in agricultural sustainability: A review. *Molecules* 21(5), 573.
- Verma, S.K., Kingsley, K., Bergen, M., English, C., Elmore, M., Kharwar, R.N., and White, J.F. 2018. Bacterial endophytes from rice cut grass (*Leersia oryzoides* L.) increase growth, promote root gravitropic response, stimulate root hair formation, and protect rice seedlings from disease. *Plant and Soil* 422(1), 223–238.
- Wang, S., Duan, Y., Chen, L., and Jin, Y. 2008. Effects of Biocontrol Bacteria Snb331 Fermentation Broth on the Rice White-tip Nematode (*Aphelenchoides besseyi*)[J]. *Journal of Henan Agricultural Sciences* 5.
- Wang, Z.M., Zhou, F.M., Lu, Y.L., Lu, H.F., Chen, Z.Y., Liu, Y.F., and Wei, W. 2004. Study on causes and control measures of small grains and erect ears in rice in Jiangsu Province. *Jiangsu Agric Sci.* 3, 33–38.
- Widyanti, A., Sunaryo, I., and Kumalasari, A.D. 2014. Reducing the dependency on rice as staple food in Indonesia—a behavior intervention approach. *Journal of ISSAAS* 20(1), 93–103.
- Xie, J., Yang, F., Wang, Y., Peng, Y., and Ji, H. 2019. Studies on the efficiency of different inoculation methods of rice white-tip nematode, *Aphelenchoides besseyi*. *Nematology* 21(7), 673–678.
- Youssef, M.M.A. 2014. The leaf and bud nematode, *Aphelenchoides besseyi*, its identification, economic importance, and control measures. A review. *Middle East Journal of Agriculture Research* 3(3), 461–464.
- Zainudin, Z., Abadi, A.L., and Aini, L.Q. 2014. Pengaruh pemberian Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (*Bacillus subtilis* dan *Pseudomonas fluorescens*) terhadap penyakit bulai pada tanaman jagung (*Zea mays* L.). *Jurnal Hama dan Penyakit Tumbuhan* 2(1), 11.